

The impact of omics and data science in cancer research and patient care

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AIMaC
INFORMA PER AIUTARE
A VIVERE CON IL CANCRO

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di Milano

COMMENTARY

Open Access

Alliance Against Cancer, the network of Italian cancer centers bridging research and care

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Abstract

Alliance Against Cancer (ACC) was established in Rome in 2002 as a consortium of six Italian comprehensive cancer centers (Founders). The aims of ACC were to promote a network among Italian oncologic institutions in order to develop specific, advanced projects in clinical and translational research. During the following years, many additional full and associate members joined ACC, that presently includes the National Institute of Health, 17 research-oriented hospitals, scientific and patient organizations. Furthermore, in the last three years ACC underwent a reorganization process that redesigned the structure, governance and major activities. The present goal of ACC is to achieve high standards of care across Italy, to implement and harmonize principles of modern personalized and precision medicine, by developing cost effective processes and to provide tailored information to cancer patients. We herein summarize some of the major initiatives that ACC is currently developing to reach its goal, including tumor genetic screening programs, establishment of clinical trial programs for cancer patients treated in Italian cancer centers, facilitate their access to innovative drugs under development, improve quality through an European accreditation process (European Organization of Cancer Institutes), and develop international partnerships. In conclusion, ACC is a growing organization, trying to respond to the need of networking in Italy and may contribute significantly to improve the way we face cancer in Europe.

Keywords: Italy, Network of cancer centers, Translational research, Cancer care, Personalized medicine, Clinical trials

Working Groups and Committees

Working Groups

Committees

- Committee for Clinical Research and Medicines Strategy
- Committee for the Coordination of the Working Groups and Related Trials
- Committee for Scientific and Institutional Relations inside the EU
- Committee for Institutional Relations
- Committee for the Ethical and Legal Aspects of Patient Relations
- Committee for Scientific and Institutional Relations outside the EU

The Lung-Oncochip

1. Genes (all coding sequences, amplifications, deletions)

Total: 182

Actionables: 164

Drivers: 33 (drivers only = 18)

2. Translocations/Rearrangements (RNA)

- 93 Total fusion targets

- 52 Actionable partner pairs (including ALK, RET, ROS1)

3. Germline Variants

- Identified in the pharmGKB database

- 81 genes; (185 variants)

ACC Genomics

The ACC Lung-Cancer Chip

164
Actionable
Genes

52
Actionable
Fusions

96
Actionable
SNPs

18
Driver
Genes

5
Driver
Fusions

**Cost: <300 €
per patient**

Patients with ≥ 1 actionable mutation

Actionable mutations per patient

In silico screening of ~500 lung-cancer patients

Validation of the Alliance Against Cancer lung panel in 1,000 patients with Non Small Cell Lung Cancer

Inclusion criteria:

- All consecutive patients with histological or cytological diagnosis of advanced (Stage IIB/IV) NSCLC, seen at each center during the study period, will be included and considered in all analyses
- ECOG PS 0-2
- Written Informed Consent

Primary Objective:

to validate the ACC - Lung Panel as a tool for molecular screening in patients with NSCLC

Comparison between the frequency of EGFR activating mutations and EML4-ALK translocation observed with NGS and routine techniques (sensitivity and specificity)

- OSR (Milan)
- Humanitas (Milan)
- IEO (Milan)
- INT (Milan)
- CRO (Aviano)
- Candiolo (Torino)
- San Martino (Genova)
- IOV (Padova)
- IRST Meldola (Forlì-Cesena)
- Reggio Emilia
- IRE-OM (Rome – 2 centers)
- IDI (Rome)
- Gemelli (Rome)
- Villa Sofia Cervello (Palermo)
- Cannizzaro (Catania)
- CROB (Potenza)
- Pascale (Napoli)
- Casa Sollievo della Sofferenza (San Giovanni Rotondo)
- Istituto Tumori (Bari)
- La Maddalena (Palermo)
- AOU (Catania)
- AOU (Parma)
- San Matteo (Pavia)

- Data upload
- Quality check
- RT progress
- Procedures
- Pipelines
- Reagent
- Global stats

- Knowledge database
- Data retrieval

ALLIANCE AGAINST CANCER DATA PORTAL.

A data portal to guide researchers and physisists toward the resources generated by the **Alliance Against Cancer organization**.

FIND OUT MORE

Radiomics WG active joint studies

Luca Boldrini

Radiomics validation of the ACC Lung Panel in Non Small Cells Lung Cancer (RATIONALE study)

Inter ACC WG study : WG Lung & WG Genomics

PI: D. Regge (Candiolo), L. Boldrini (Gemelli)

Satellite study to ACC Lung

18 centers authorized - 10 centers active: 800 patients expected

Primary aim

Development of radiogenomics models for :

- prediction of EGR, EML4-ALK, cMET, ROS1, RET, BRAF/KRAS or no mutational status
- treatment response prediction and overall survival

Secondary aims

- Delta radiomics applications for the available dataset
- Development of clinical decision support systems (DSS)
- Development of an automatic segmentation algorithm for lung volumes (CNN)

The GerSom panel: selection of PanCancer somatic and germline drivers

Cell

Pathogenic Germline Variants in 10,389 Adult Cancers

Graphical Abstract

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In Brief

A pan-cancer analysis identifies hundreds of predisposing germline variants.

Article

Cell

Comprehensive Characterization of Cancer Driver Genes and Mutations

Graphical Abstract

Authors

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In Brief

A comprehensive analysis of oncogenic driver genes and mutations in >9,000 tumors across 33 cancer types highlights the prevalence of clinically actionable cancer driver events in TCGA tumor samples.

Article

Gersom: the ACC diagnostic panel

- **Aiming to unify germline (risk) and somatic (predictive/prognostic) information**
- **A large panel including:**
 - **467 full-length genes**
 - 299 pan-cancer driver genes
 - 172 risk-associated genes
 - 135 actionable genes
 - 110 genes with optimized design for Copy Number Variants
 - **196 pharmacogenomics variants**
- **Total genomic space: 1.8 Mb**
- **TMB calling plus MSI/MMR deficiency, possibly HRD**

Genome analysis

TMBleR: a bioinformatic tool to optimize TMB estimation and predictive power

Laura Fancello^{1,†}, Alessandro Guida^{2,3,4,†}, Gianmaria Frige²,
 Arnaud Gerard Michel Ceol², Gabriele Babini⁵, Giovanni Luca Scaglione⁶,
 Mario Zanfardino⁷, Tommaso Mazza⁸, Lorenzo Ferrando⁹, Pier Giuseppe Pelicci^{2,10}
 and Luca Mazzarella^{2,11,*}

The **analysis module** provides functions to select specific groups of variants to include in TMB calculation from a combination of predefined categories (synonymous, non-synonymous, frameshifts, non-sense mutations; customizable VAF thresholds, cancer driver-associated mutations) or any set of genomic positions. Then, it calculates and plots TMB values from different patients and/or using different variant filters.

The **simulation module** allows to exploit WES/WGS datasets to simulate TMB quantification for different variant filters and targeted panels. It provides three types of output: (i) analytical performance, i.e. a scatterplot with the correlation between panel-derived and WES-derived TMB values and its regression parameters; (ii) clinical performance, if categorical information on clinical outcome is available in the dataset, as TMB distribution boxplots by outcome classes (e.g. responders and non-responders) and as sensitivity/specificity analyses using ROC curves.

Analysis Module

- Define a set of filters for the mutational profile

Legend
 NC = NoCancer mutations
 NS = No synonymous mutations
 VAF = variant allele frequency threshold

- Estimate TMB

Sample	Filter	TMB per Mb
Sample 1	Filter 1	101.54
Sample 1	Filter 2	41.91
Sample 1	Filter 3	97.78
...		...
Sample 2	Filter 7	45.13
Sample 2	Filter 8	56.42

- Visualize TMB for each sample stratified by mutational profile filters

Simulation Module

- Read WES design
- Subset WES to simulate panel
- Define a set of filters for the mutational profile

- Performance comparison
 Genomic panel vs WES for each TMB filter

- Add clinical data
 Clinical performance simulation

Cancer Patient

Gersom

Genomic profile
of every patient
(tumor+germline)

- Detection of actionable somatic mutations (135 genes)
- MSI status
- Mutational burden
- ➤ Transcriptome
- ➤ Detection of germline pharmacogenomic variants
- ➤ Detection of driver-gene mutations (299 genes)

- Treatment-stratification
- ➤ Drug-toxicity
- ➤ New stratification markers

- Identification of germline variants for cancer risk: 172 genes
- ➤ Polymorphism analysis

Mapping of
germline risk in
family members

- Cancer prevention plans
- Polygenic Risk Score

- Registry of Somatic cancer-mutations
- Registry of Germline cancer-risk pattern

2020-2022 output 4,000 patients:

1,500 ovary
1,500 breast (< 40 years and TNBC)
1,000 colorectal (< 50 years)

Comparison of Universal Genetic Testing vs Guideline-Directed Targeted Testing for Patients With Hereditary Cancer Syndrome

2984

13.3% PGVs found using CGP

48.4% of them would not have been detected by phenotype or family history–based testing criteria using the 2018 NCCN, NSGC, or ACMG guidelines

17.6% with PGVs had family members undergoing no-cost cascade FVT

Machine learning-based reclassification of germline variants of unknown significance: The RENOVO algorithm

Valentina Favalli,^{1,3} Giulia Tini,^{1,3} Emanuele Bonetti,¹ Gianluca Vozza,¹ Alessandro Guida,^{1,2} Sara Gandini,¹ Pier Giuseppe Pelicci,¹ and Luca Mazzarella^{1,*}

Summary

The increasing scope of genetic testing allowed by next-generation sequencing (NGS) dramatically increased the number of genetic variants to be interpreted as pathogenic or benign for adequate patient management. Still, the interpretation process often fails to deliver a clear classification, resulting in either variants of unknown significance (VUSs) or variants with conflicting interpretation of pathogenicity (CIP); these represent a major clinical problem because they do not provide useful information for decision-making, causing a large fraction of genetically determined disease to remain undertreated. We developed a machine learning (random forest)-based tool, RENOVO, that classifies variants as pathogenic or benign on the basis of publicly available information and provides a pathogenicity likelihood score (PLS). Using the same feature classes recommended by guidelines, we trained RENOVO on established pathogenic/benign variants in ClinVar (training set accuracy = 99%) and tested its performance on variants whose interpretation has changed over time (test set accuracy = 95%). We further validated the algorithm on additional datasets including unreported variants validated either through expert consensus (ENIGMA) or laboratory-based functional techniques (on *BRCA1/2* and *SCN5A*). On all datasets, RENOVO outperformed existing automated interpretation tools. On the basis of the above validation metrics, we assigned a defined PLS to all existing ClinVar VUSs, proposing a reclassification for 67% with >90% estimated precision. RENOVO provides a validated tool to reduce the fraction of uninterpreted or misinterpreted variants, tackling an area of unmet need in modern clinical genetics.

The ACC GerSom Trial: 21 centers

- OSR (Milan)
- Humanitas (Milan)
- IEO (Milan)
- INT (Milan)
- CRO (Aviano)
- Candiolo (Torino)
- San Martino (Genova)
- IOV (Padova)
- IRST Meldola (Forlì-Cesena)
- Reggio Emilia

- IRE (Rome)
- San Camillo (Rome)
- Gemelli (Rome)
- Castellana Grotte (Bari)
- Policlinico V.E. (Catania)
- CROB (Potenza)
- Pascale (Napoli)
- Casa Sollievo della Sofferenza (San Giovanni Rotondo)
- Istituto Tumori (Bari)
- Policlinico Giaccone (Palermo)
- AOU (Catania)

GERSOM STUDY

Enrolment

2128

enrolled patients

September 2023

Alliance Against Cancer has established a partnership with the **Center for Research and Development in Information and Communication Technologies** of the National Institute for Nuclear Physics

ALLEANZA
CONTRO
IL CANCRO

Infrastructures

- Physical (server, storage & connectivity)
- Backup
- Virtualization (Test & Production)

INFN provides ACC with an IT platform for the management and analysis of biomedical and genomic big data

The NEW ENGLAND JOURNAL of MEDICINE

SOUNDING BOARD

Real-World Evidence — What Is It and What Can It Tell Us?

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Gerald J. Dal Pan, M.D., M.H.S., Gerry W. Gray, Ph.D., Thomas Gross, M.D., M.P.H.,
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Peter W. Marks, M.D., Ph.D., Melissa A. Robb, B.S.N., M.S., Jeffrey Shuren, M.D., J.D.,
Robert Temple, M.D., Janet Woodcock, M.D., Lilly Q. Yue, Ph.D., and Robert M. Califf, M.D.

N ENGL J MED 375;23 NEJM.ORG DECEMBER 8, 2016

Real-World Evidence

- It refers to information on health care that is derived from multiple sources **outside** typical clinical research settings such as **randomized clinical trials**, including **electronic health records (EHRs)**, **claims and billing data**, **product and disease registries**, and data gathered through **personal devices** and **health applications**.
- Key to understanding the usefulness of real-world evidence is an appreciation of its potential for **complementing** the knowledge gained from **traditional clinical trials**, whose well-known **limitations** make it **difficult to generalize findings to larger, more inclusive populations of patients, providers**, and health care delivery systems or settings that reflect **actual use in practice**.

Inversion of chromosome 2p results in constitutively active EML4-ALK fusion protein. Structural rearrangements involving the *ALK* gene drive a number of cancers. In non-small-cell lung cancer, the most common structural rearrangement involving the *ALK* locus is an inversion of a portion of chromosome 2p, juxtaposing the 5' portion of *EML4* to the 3' portion of *ALK*. *ALK* is not normally transcribed in adult lung, but under the control of the *EML4* promoter, the EML4-ALK fusion protein is expressed in lung tissue, and the dimerization domain of EML4 (dark purple bars) permits unregulated dimerization of the TK domain, constitutively activating downstream pathways.

Alectinib versus Crizotinib in Untreated *ALK*-Positive Non-Small-Cell Lung Cancer

Hazard ratio for disease progression or death,
0.47 (95% CI, 0.34–0.65)
P<0.001 by log-rank test

Roche acquires Flatiron Health in \$1.9 billion deal

<https://www.zdnet.com/article/roche-acquires-flatiron-health-in-1-9-billion-deal/>

It is hoped the deal will ramp up cancer research through healthcare data and analytics.

By Charlie Osborne for [Between the Lines](#) | February 16, 2018 -- 11:43 GMT (03:43 PST) | Topic: [Innovation](#)

[Technology](#) [Company](#) [Publications](#) [Careers](#) [Blog](#)

Cancer is smart.
Together, we can
be smarter.

Accelerating the fight against cancer requires the entire industry to work together. Our products connect community oncologists, academics, hospitals, life science researchers and regulators on a shared technology platform. Together, we can learn from the experience of our patients.

Flatiron's data helped Roche expand access to Alectinib, which was approved by FDA in November 2017, as first-line treatment for ALK-positive NSCLC.

The Flatiron database was able to support the access of Alectinib in different countries because it allows to compare USA real-world data to the way that Alectinib performed in clinical trials.

Health Big-data

Virtual Institutes of the Italian Network of IRCCS

- ✓ Prevent diseases
- ✓ Personalize care
- ✓ Improve the quality of life of patients

The Italian Ministry of Health is addressing this change in order to respond to the new needs of the country, where the population is ageing and has a growing need to be treated and assisted especially in the area of diseases that most affect the elderly: oncological, neurological and cardiovascular diseases.

The general objective of this program is to accelerate the transition to Precision and Personalized Medicine in the country, through the creation of an innovative national organization of IRCCS and the development of digital technologies for the construction of health and disease models (Human Avatar).

The specific objective of this project is the creation of a common platform for the various IRCCS for the collection, exchange and analysis of clinical and scientific data (**Health Big-data**). The clinical-scientific synergies and the creation of an economy of scale between the IRCCSs will lead to a concrete advancement of knowledge on prediction, prevention and personalized therapies in the reference areas of the three networks: **cancer, neurological diseases and cardiovascular diseases**.

The challenge: Systematic collection of high-resolution multi-dimensional data

Generation of Patient/Person Digital Avatars

Generation of a Universal Knowledge Resource to manage health and care

Systematic collection
of high-resolution
data across millions
of patients

Real-time knowledge
generation (artificial
intelligence systems)

Disease re-classification
(not based on human-
defined disease classes)

High-definition Prevention
and Treatment

Single-patient
treatment decisions
(intelligent-decision support)

Real-time data generation and sharing

ICSC

Centro Nazionale HPC,
Big Data
e Quantum Computing

Cloud national infrastructure for supercomputing

Hub & Spoke organization:

10 vertical spokes for technology developments and software applications

400 M€ Total Budget

188 M€ Cloud Infrastructure

The infrastructure core is **Leonardo**, one of the eight **pre-exascale** supercomputers that will form the **EuroHPC** European high-performance computing network via the European GÉANT network, through a dual 100 Gbps connection to the **GARR national network**. The new machine, with an aggregate computing power > 250 PFLOPS (**F**loating point **O**perations **P**er **S**econd) ranks among the top 5 supercomputers in the TOP500.

Davide Salomoni

The federation process: Network platforms

The federation process: IRCSS integration

Network data platform

Federated data platform

IRCCS integration

Progressive integration of IRCCSs into the Network data platforms and in the Federated data platform

Working Group (coordinated by Politecnico di Milano):

- Discussion site among the 51 IRCCSs on specific topics
- Upgrading the infrastructure of each IRCCS to ensure interoperability of clinical-scientific data

Beyond The Rome Trial

The Rome Trial has completed enrollment with over 1750 patients

Beyond The Rome Trial

Locally advanced and/or metastatic disease (not treatable with potentially curative surgery)

Availability of an extended genomic profiling from tumor tissue or blood (high-density gene panels)

60 centers ↓ 4,500 pts

Molecular Tumor Board

THERAPY AT CHOICE OF PHYSICIAN (AIOM guidelines)

↓ 1,000 pts

Randomization

GENOMIC-BASED TAILORED according to MTB discussion (using drugs from those available in the trial)

Primary Objective: efficacy (PFS) and QoL benefit (PROs)

- **Identification of subgroups with an enhanced treatment effect**
 - **drug discovery phase**

- **4 billion euro** for actions addressing cancer, from:
 - DG RTD –Cancer Mission
 - DG SANTE – EU4Health programme
 - DG RTD – Horizon Europe
 - DG CONNECT – Digital Europe
- **4 key action areas** to tackle the entire disease pathway :
 - Prevention
 - Early Detection
 - Diagnosis & Treatment
 - Quality of Life
- **10 flagship initiatives** and **32 supporting actions**

Europe's Beating Cancer Plan proposes actions for all stages of the disease

PREVENTION

- ◆ 4 out of every 10 cases of cancer are preventable. The Plan will draw attention to:
- ◆ **taxation's** role for tobacco and alcohol
- ◆ reducing exposure to **carcinogens** in the work place and in the environment
- ◆ **Farm to Fork Strategy** to promote healthy diets

DIAGNOSIS

- Address **gaps in knowledge**
- **Digitalisation** reduces detection time
- **Technical support** to Member States
- **Regulatory support** reduces inequalities

TREATMENT

- ▶ Improved **treatment times**
- ▶ Incentivising **innovation**
- ▶ Pharmaceutical strategy for **affordable therapies**
- ▶ **European Health Data Space** promotes exchanges and research

QUALITY OF LIFE OF PATIENTS & SURVIVORS

- + improving **quality of life** for patients and survivors
- + Avoiding **discrimination**
- + **Psychological support**
- + **Back-to-work support**

ACC in Europe

4.UNCAN.eu

a European initiative to UNderstand CANcer

creating a
**FEDERATED CANCER RESEARCH
DATA HUB**

fed with
**RESEARCH
USE CASES**

involving
**PATIENT ADVOCATES
EU CITIZENS**

solving
**INEQUITIES BETWEEN
MEMBER STATES**

The creation of a **federated digital platform** where **researchers from all over the world share and have access to high-quality cancer research data**

Generate new breakthroughs on cancer that enhance cancer prevention, early diagnosis, and treatment strategies

A **Coordination and Support Action (CSA)** under the Mission on Cancer will deliver a **blueprint** for the establishment of a fully-fledged, sustainable platform managed by Member States, associated countries & stakeholders.

DECISION-MAKING

—→ Appoints
- - - - -→ Advises

EXECUTIVE

Administrative and Management Unit

OPERATIVE

CENTRAL NODE

Platform co-creation with researchers

A set of **use cases** will trigger the federation

- **Cancer research challenges** to be addressed at the supranational level
- Transnational use cases will **generate multimodal data** to **initiate the network of National Nodes**
- **EU-funded calls** for use cases will provide an **incentive** for researchers to share the generated data in UNCAN.eu

WP2 – Bottom-up consensus process

- More than **300 cancer experts** appointed through an open call mechanism
 - Translational and basic scientists
 - Clinical researchers
 - Data scientists
 - Patient advocates

- **32 European countries and patient advocacy organizations** represented in the Expert Working Groups

- Six pre-defined **areas of research**
 - Prevention
 - Early Diagnosis
 - Sensitivity and Resistance to Therapy
 - Pediatric Cancer
 - Cancer and Ageing
 - Survivorship

- **Delphi methodology** to identify top-ranked priorities of research within each area

Consensus Workshops

Barcelona

Use Cases, part 1

March
2023

Rome

Use Cases, part 2

May
2023

UNCAN.eu
2nd Face-to-Face
4.UNCAN.eu
Consensus meeting
May 22nd-23rd, 2023 Rome

Block 3: Roundtable discussions

FUNDING & INNOVATION: Antonio Katsaris, Shafiq Skandar, Johannes Zuber
- What **funding structures** may stimulate cross-funding results in these sectors? -> multi-disciplinary, multi-country, academic, industry, patients partnerships, integration of basic/translational research?
- What **schemes of funding distribution** could accelerate progress most effectively? -> multi-therapeutic, grants, program grants to support capacity building and infrastructure development, grants to foster innovation and technology transfer in, transdisciplinary exchange of solutions?
- What **funding strategies** could more effectively achieve solutions and Europe's climate research funding in Europe?

DIVERSITY: Mado Mado, Anja Kolar, Sida, Xelena Sanchez-Diego
- How can we better **support the development of early career scientists** in research careers?
- How can we address **underrepresentation of certain geographic regions** in research careers?
- How can we effectively promote **diversity and inclusion** in research careers?

PATIENT ENGAGEMENT: Ingrida Čiurpaitė, Shafiq Skandar, Johannes Zuber
- How can we better **support and coordinate learning** in research careers? -> formal, informal, experiential, and expectations?
- Where can **bidirectional communication** between research and patients be improved?
- What **training activities** could be supported to improve the **scientific literacy** and **responsibility** of patients to contribute to research activities more effectively?
- How can **patient, advocate, and organization participation** in the design of research projects to their perspectives can influence research activities?
- What **innovative strategies** would be possible for increasing **effective engagement and involvement** of patients in cancer research activities?

can.heal

Building the EU Cancer and Health Genomics Platform

- To build on **ongoing studies** to promote the application of genomics to improve **diagnosis and treatment** of cancer patients as well as to improve our understanding of individual **susceptibility**
 - **Genomics for Public Health**: building clinical utility for polygenic risk scores, cancer in pregnancy and Family-based testing in pediatric leukemia
 - **Cancer Diagnostics and Treatment for All**: applying NGS and liquid biopsy in clinical settings and develop harmonized tools for data analysis, interpretation and decision support
- The final goal of the project is to **establish recommendations** for initiatives into the EU health system

The Gemelli Program of Precision Oncology

Fondazione Policlinico Universitario Agostino Gemelli IRCCS

Gemelli

Fondazione Policlinico Universitario Agostino Gemelli IRCCS
Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore

1,611
Total beds

2,850,291
Outpatients services

80,994
Surgical procedures

around 50,000
Cancer patients

data from Mission statement 2022

Comprehensive analysis of actionable genes (first year 2022)

Assay: TruSight Oncology 500™ (TSO500, Illumina®)*

ABL1	BRD4	CUX1	FAM175A	GATA6	IGF1	MAP3K13	NOTCH4	POLE	RPTOR	TAF1
ABL2	BRIP1	CXCR4	FAM46C	GEN1	IGF1R	MAP3K14	NPM1	PPARG	RUNX1	TBX3
ACVR1	BTG1	CYLD	FANCA	GID4	IGF2	MAP3K4	NRAS	PPM1D	RUNX1T1	TCEB1
ACVR1B	BTK	DAXX	FANCC	GLI1	IKBKE	MAPK1	NRG1	PPP2R1A	RYBP	TCF3
AKT1	C11orf90	DCUN1D1	FANGC2	GNA11	IKZF1	MAPK3	NSD1	PPP2R2A	SDHA	TCF7L2
AKT2	CALR	DDR2	FANCE	GNA13	IL10	MAX	NTRK1	PPP6C	SDHAF2	TEPC
AKT3	CARD11	DDX41	FANCF	GNAQ	IL7R	MCL1	NTRK2	PRDM1	SDHB	TERT
ALK	CASP8	DHX15	FANCG	GNAS	INH4A	MOC1	NTRK3	PRES2	SDHC	TET1
ALOX12B	CBFB	DICER1	FANCI	GPR124	INH4B	MDM2	NUP93	PRKAR1A	SDHD	TET2
ANKRD11	CBL	DSS3	FANCL	GPS2	INFP4A	MDM4	NUTM1	PRKCI	SETBP1	TFE3
ANKRD26	CCND1	DNAJB1	FAS	GREM1	INFP4B	MED12	PAK1	PRKDC	SETD2	TRFC
APC	CCND2	DNMT1	FAT1	GRIN2A	INSR	MEF2B	PAK3	PRSS8	SF3B1	TGFBP1
AR	CCND3	DNMT3A	FBXW7	GRM3	IRF2	MEN1	PAK7	PTCH1	SH2B3	TGFBR2
ARAF	CCNE1	DNMT3B	FGF1	GSK3B	IRF4	MET	PALB2	PTEN	SH2D1A	TMEM127
ARFRP1	CD274	DOT1L	FGF10	H3F3A	IRS1	MGA	PARK2	PTPN11	SHQ1	TMPRSS2
ARID1A	CD276	E2F3	FGF14	H3F3B	IRS2	MITF	PARP1	PTPRD	SLIT2	TNFAIP3
ARID1B	CD74	EED	FGF19	H3F3C	JAK1	MLH1	PAX3	PTPRS	SLX4	TNFRSF14
ARID2	CD79A	EGFL7	FGF2	HGF	JAK2	MLL	PAX5	PTPRT	SMAD2	TOP1
ARID5B	CD79B	EGFR	FGF23	HIST1H1C	JAK3	MLL3	PAX7	QKI	SMAD3	TOP2A
ASXL1	CD373	EIF1AX	FGF3	HIST1H2BD	JUN	MPL	PAX8	RAB35	SMAD4	TP53
ASXL2	CDH1	EIF4A2	FGF4	HIST1H3A	KAT6A	MRE11A	PBRM1	RAC1	SMARCA4	TP63
ATM	CDK12	EIF4E	FGF5	HIST1H3B	KDM5A	MSH2	PDCD1	RAD21	SMARCB1	TRAF2
ATR	CDK4	EML4	FGF6	HIST1H3C	KDM5C	MSH3	PDCD1LG2	RAD50	SMARCD1	TRAF7
ATRX	CDK6	EP300	FGF7	HIST1H3D	KDM6A	MSH6	PDGFRA	RAD51	SMC1A	TSC1
AURKA	CDK8	EPCAM	FGF8	HIST1H3E	KDR	MST1	PDGFRB	RAD51B	SMC3	TSC2
AURKB	CDKN1A	EPHA3	FGF9	HIST1H3F	KEAP1	MST1R	PDK1	RAD51C	SMO	TSHR
AXIN1	CDKN1B	EPHA5	FGFR1	HIST1H3G	KEL	MTOR	PDPK1	RAD51D	SIN3AIP	UZAF1
AXIN2	CDKN2A	EPHA7	FGFR2	HIST1H3H	KIF5B	MUTYH	PGR	RAD52	SODC1	VEGFA
AXL	CDKN2B	EPHB1	FGFR3	HIST1H3I	KIT	MYB	PHF6	RAD54L	SOX10	VHL
B3M	CDKN2C	ERBB2	FGFR4	HIST1H3J	KLF4	MYC	PHOX2B	RAF1	SOK17	VTCN1
BAP1	CEBPA	ERBB3	FH1	HIST2H3A	KLHL6	MYCL1	PIK3C2B	RANBP2	SOX2	WSP3
BAR1	CEBPA	ERBB4	FLCN	HIST2H3C	KMT2B	MYCN	PIK3C2G	RARA	SOX9	WT1
BBC3	CHD2	ERCC1	FLI1	HIST2H3D	KMT2C	MYD88	PIK3C3	RASA1	SPEN	XAP
BCL10	CHD4	ERCC2	FLT1	HIST3H3	KMT2D	MYO10	PIK3CA	RB1	SPOP	XPO1
BCL2	CHEK1	ERCC3	FLT3	HLA-A	KIFAS	NAB2	PIK3CB	RBM10	SPTA1	XRCC2
BCL2L1	CHEK2	ERCC4	FLT4	HLA-B	LAMP1	NBN	PIK3CD	RECQL4	SRC	YAP1
BCL2L1	CIC	ERCC5	FOXA1	HLA-C	LATS1	NCOA3	PIK3CG	REL	SRSF2	YES1
BCL2L2	CREBBP	ERG	FOXL2	HNF1A	LATS2	NCOR1	PIK3R1	RET	STAG1	ZBTB2
BCL6	CRKL	ERF1	FOXO1	HNR1P	LMO1	NEGR1	PIK3R2	RFWD2	STAG2	ZBTB7A
BCOR	CHL2	ESR1	FOXP1	HOXB13	LRRP1B	NF1	PIK3R3	RHEB	STAT3	ZFYX3
BCORL1	CSF1R	ETS1	FRS2	HRAS	LYN	NF2	PIM1	RHOA	STAT4	ZNF217
BCR	CSF3R	ETV1	FUBP1	HSD3B1	LZTR1	NFE2L2	PLCG2	RICTOR	STAT5A	ZNF703
BIRC3	CSNK1A1	ETV4	FYN	HSP90AA1	MAGI2	NFKBIA	PLK2	RIT1	STAT5B	ZRSR2
BLM	CTCF	ETV5	GABRA6	ICOSLG	MALT1	NKX2-1	PMAIP1	RNF43	STK11	
BMP1R1A	CTLA4	ETV6	GATA1	ID3	MAP2K1	NKX3-1	PMS1	ROS1	STK40	
BRAF	CTNNA1	EWSR1	GATA2	IDH1	MAP2K2	NOTCH1	PMS2	RPS6KA4	SUFU	
BRC1A1	CTNNA1	EZH2	GATA3	IDH2	MAP2K4	NOTCH2	PNRC1	RPS6KB1	SUZ12	
BRC1A2	CUL3	FAM123B	GATA4	IFNGR1	MAP3K1	NOTCH3	POLD1	RPS6KB2	SYK	

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ABL1	BCL2	CSF1R	ESR1	EWSR1	FLI1	KIF5B	MSH2	NRG1	PAX7	RAF1
AKT3	BRAF	EGFR	ETS1	FGFR1	FLT1	KIT	MYC	NTRK1	PDGFRA	RET
ALK	BRC1A1	EML4	ETV1	FGFR2	FLT3	MET	NOTCH1	NTRK2	PDGFRB	ROS1
AR	BRC1A2	ERBB2	ETV4	FGFR3	JAK2	MLL	NOTCH2	NTRK3	PIK3CA	RPS6KB1
AXL	CDK4	ERG	ETV5	FGFR4	KDR	MLL3	NOTCH3	PAX3	PPARG	TMPRSS2

LEGEND

- PRIMARY LINE (HYBRID: RESEARCH & DIAGNOSTICS)
- ALTERNATIVE LINE
- RESEARCH LINE
- DIAGNOSTIC LINE
- - - EXIT LINE
- CHECKPOINT
- KEY JUNCTION

can.heal

Clinical Arm

